

APPLICATION OF PHYSIOTHERAPY IN SANATORIUM TREATMENT

Komilova Dildora Alisherovna

Assistant at the Department of Anatomy and Microanatomy
Central Asian Medical University.

Fergana, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10468124>

Abstract: The article is devoted to the current problem of treatment using various physiotherapeutic procedures in sanatorium conditions.

Key words: sanatorium treatment, physiotherapeutic procedures.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена актуальной проблеме лечению с помощью различных физиотерапевтических процедур в санаторных условиях.

Ключевые слова: санаторное лечение, физиотерапевтические процедуры.

Introduction. Every person strives for comfort. You want to experience this feeling of comfort constantly, both at work and at home, in everyday life, and of course in your health. The desire to be healthy is, first of all, taking care of yourself and your family. This problem can be solved with the help of sanatorium-resort treatment.

Sanatorium treatment involves the use of physiotherapy. It affects the human body for medicinal purposes: water, heat, cold, light, electricity, electromagnetic field, ultrasound. The therapeutic effect of many simple physiotherapeutic procedures is explained primarily by the presence of a close neuro-reflex connection between internal organs and individual areas of the skin that have a common innervation.

Providing a strong irritating effect on the peripheral skin receptors of these areas. The methods, methods and means used to treat human diseases are extremely diverse. Along with drugs and surgical methods, there are many types of non-drug therapeutic effects. The main place among them is occupied by healing physical factors.

The main part. There are natural ones - climate, air, solar energy, water (mineral waters and with an admixture of salts), healing mud. Natural physical factors are studied and used by spa therapy. Natural factors have been used for treatment since ancient times. Physiotherapy has become an important element of medical care for the population. The rational use of physical non-drug factors significantly increases the effectiveness of complex treatment and rehabilitation of patients, reduces the period of temporary disability, reduces disability, accelerating the return of patients to active life and creative work.

Physiotherapeutic procedures have a variety of effects on the human body. As a result of their use, pain disappears or decreases, the functional state of organs is normalized, the activity of inflammatory processes decreases, the trophism of tissues and organs improves, and the general condition improves. The use of various physiotherapeutic procedures has been relevant for many years, since physiotherapeutic procedures are included in various programs for the complex treatment of many diseases. The provision of sanatorium-resort treatment is considered as an effective area of medical rehabilitation.

There are various types and methods of physiotherapeutic treatment. There are several dozen treatment methods in the arsenal of physiotherapy. They can be

classified based on which physical factor of influence is the leading one. There are several dozen methods of physiotherapeutic treatment. There are types of physiotherapeutic treatment based on application:электрического тока - электротерапия;

- magnetic field - magnetotherapy;
- light - phototherapy;
- mechanical factors - mechanotherapy;
- atmospheric pressure - barotherapy;
- air environment - arotherapy and climatotherapy;
- thermophysical effects - thermotherapy;
- therapeutic mud - peloidotherapy;
- water and mineral water solutions - hydrotherapy and balneotherapy.

Absolute contraindications to any physiotherapeutic procedures are:

- oncological diseases;
- serious pathologies of the heart and lungs;
- pregnancy and lactation;
- renal or liver failure;
- acute mental disorders;
- skin diseases in the acute stage;
- acute infectious diseases.

Sanatorium-resort treatment can be considered the most natural and physiological, since for many diseases, especially in the period of remission, i.e. after the disappearance of acute manifestations, it is the most effective. Various non-drug types of treatment are widely used in complex spa treatment:

- hydrotherapy;
- diet therapy;
- physiotherapy;
- massage;
- acupuncture,
- use of various devices.

Depending on the predominance of one or another healing natural factor, resorts are divided into:

- climatic;
- balneological;
- mud therapy.

Conclusion. Every vacationer in the sanatorium first of all takes care of his health, chooses the time for treatment, and this is both an excellent preventive measure for the prevention of various diseases and active recreation.

Sanatorium physiotherapeutic treatment is simply necessary today, as it gives every vacationer the opportunity to receive treatment and relax.

References:

1. Справочник по физиотерапии / Под ред. В. Г.Ясногородского.- М., 1992–213с.

2. Техника и методики физиотерапевтических процедур: Справочник / Под ред. В. М.Боголюбова.- М., 2002- 168с.
3. Улащик В. С., Лукомский И. В. Общая физиотерапия. - Книжный дом, 2004. - 512 с.
4. OR Parpiyeva, AD Ostanauqulov //Health theory// Международный научно-практический журнал "Форум молодых ученых". Вып №6 (34) 2019. 26-29 pages.
5. Odinakhan Rakhmanovna Parpieva, & Davlatov Hamidjon Dilshodjon ogli. (2023). HEALTH IS THE HIGHEST VALUE. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 1(11), 760-763.
6. Bakhritdinov, F. S., Matkarimov, Z. T., Azimova, M. T., Saatova, U. M., Komilova, D. N., & Elmurodova, N. B. (2022). Features of Pregnancy Management in Kidney Transplant Recipients. Experimental and Clinical Transplantation: Official Journal of the Middle East Society for Organ Transplantation, 20(Suppl 4), 92-97.
7. Bakhritdinov, F. S., Ibadov, R. A., Azimova, M. T., Matkarimov, Z. T., Komilova, D. N., & Elmurodova, N. B. (2022). Incidence of Coronavirus Infection in Patients Undergoing Kidney Transplant During the Pandemic Period in Uzbekistan. Experimental and clinical transplantation: official journal of the Middle East Society for Organ Transplantation, 20(Suppl 4), 74-79.
8. Ibadov, R. A., Sh, B. F., Matkarimov, Z. T., Komilova, D. N., & Elmurodova, N. B. (2021). MANAGEMENT OF PATIENTS WITH KIDNEY TRANSPLANTATION DURING THE GLOBAL PANDEMIC COVID-19: SITUATION IN UZBEKISTAN. British Medical Journal, 1(1.2).
9. DILDORA SHAVKATOVNA KOMILOVA. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF BASIC SKILLS IN TEACHING SYSTEM. International Scientific and Current Research Conferences, 1(1), 392-398.
10. KOMILOVA, D. S., & GULCHIROY, X. (2023). ANALYSIS OF EMOTIONAL WORDS IN ARTISTIC TRANSLATIONS.
11. Komilova, D. (2022). GIVING THE LEXICON OF EMOTIONAL EVALUATION IN LITERARY TRANSLATION. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(Special Issue 29), 34-39.
12. M.T.Botirov,D.X.Tilavoldiyeva,M.A,Dabidov "THE CONCEPT OF SUBSTRATE IN HYDROPONICS!" "The world of science and innovation"(October14-16,2020).
13. BOTIROV, M., NORMATOVA, S. A., DABIDOV, M., & TILAVOLDIYEVA, D. (2021). DETERMINATION OF FERTILITY OF HYDROPONIC SUBSTRATES IN THE EXAMPLE OF TOMATO PLANTS. Asian Journal of Advances in Research, 41-45.
14. Botirov, M. T., Tilavoldiyeva, D. X., & Dabidov, M. A. (2020, October). THE CONCEPT OF SUBSTRATE IN HYDROPONICS! In The 3rd International scientific and practical conference "The world of science and innovation"(October 14-16, 2020) Cognum Publishing House, London, United Kingdom. 2020. 637 p. (p. 27).
15. Aliyeva, G., Holmirzayeva, M., & Ikromiddinov, A. (2023). PHYSIOLOGY OF CARDIAC ACTIVITY. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(10 Part 2), 91-95.
16. Абдумуталиповна, А. Г., & Рахимжанович, А. Ф. (2023). Физиологические Особенности Психического Развития Детей Дошкольного Возраста. International Journal of Formal Education, 2(7), 79-83.
17. Zafarbek Mirzaolimovich Komilov, & Qo'chqorov Oybek G'ulomovich. (2023). UBAYDULLOH KANHOL – XVI ASR O'RTA SHARQ YIRIK OKULISTI . Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(15), 217-220.

18. Камалова, Д. (2023). РОЛЬ МИКРОФЛОРЫ КИШЕЧНОГО ТРАКТА В ИММУННОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук, 3(12), 205-208.
19. Худойбердиева, Д., Сариева, Х., Хамраева, У., & Джурабекова, А. (2013). Результаты ээг исследований у детей с гиперкинетическими синдромами. Журнал вестник врача, 1(1), 190-193.
20. Хамроева, У., Сариева, Х., Худойбердиева, Д., & Джурабекова, А. (2013). Клинико-неврологический статус у детей со спинномозговыми грыжами. Журнал вестник врача, 1(1), 179-182.
21. Tilavoldieva, D. X., & Botirov, M. T. (2020). Method of hydroponics and historical, and modern. In Materials of the Republican Scientific-Practical Conference. The role of innovation in improving the quality of medicine and education, Fergana.
22. Dildora Ismoilova. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF TRANSLITERATION IN LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10459181>.
23. Ismoilova, D. (2022). SEMANTIC FEATURES OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY TERMINOLOGY IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(5), 194-196.
24. Кураматова, Ш. А. (2023). УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ КЛЕТОК ПЕЧЕНИ, ИНФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ВИРУСОМ ГЕПАТИТА В, ПУТЕМ ОБОГАЩЕНИЯ СОСТАВА ПИЩИ БИОЛОГИЧЕСКИ АКТИВНЫМИ ВЕЩЕСТВАМИ. "GERMANY" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: ACHIEVEMENTS, INNOVATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS, 9(1).
25. Sh. A. Kuramatova. (2023). Biotechnology for Enriching the Composition of Feed of Patients with Viral Hepatitis. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(6), 1350-1351.
26. Kuramatova, S. A. (2024). BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE FOOD SUPPLEMENTS FOR THE CORRECTION OF DISORDERS THAT OCCUR WITH VIRAL HEPATITIS B. In INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF MEDICAL SCIENCES AND CLINICAL RESEARCH (Vol. 4, Number 1, pp. 5-8).
27. Kamalova, D. (2023). The value of the universal progressive model in working with mothers and children in the primary care system. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 20, 60-62.